

SYNTHESIS OF A COMPLETELY REDUCED ANALOGUE OF HEXESTROL
1 : 2-DIETHYL-1-(4-METHOXYCYCLOHEXYL)-2-(4-ISOAMYL-
CYCLOHEXYL)-ETHANE

By (Miss) SINDHU PARKHI

1 : 2-Diethyl-1-(4-methoxycyclohexyl)-2-(4-isoamylcyclohexyl)-ethane (III), obtained from 4-methoxyhexahydropropiophenone and the Grignard compound of ethyl-*p*-isoamylhexahydrobenzyl bromide, on dehydration with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid at 120° furnished the corresponding ethylene (IV) which on reduction with Adam's catalyst yielded the desired completely reduced product (V).

In a scheme to prepare antirachitic substances it was thought desirable to synthesise a completely reduced analogue of hexestrol with the modification of having a long alkyl chain at the end instead of a hydroxy group. This might possess antirachitic properties as its structural resemblance is apparent with calciferol. A corresponding relationship between hexestrol and estrone is well known.

[Reduced analogue of hexestrol]

[Calciferol]

The synthesis of the methyl ether of this compound has been achieved and is described herein.

The methyl ether of ethyl 4-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate was prepared by the method of Owen and Robins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 326); attempts to benzylate ethyl ester of the carboxylic acid resulted in a poor yield of the benzyl ether. The corresponding acid was obtained as an oil. The acid chloride of this acid was converted into 4-methoxyhexahydropropiophenone (I), using a cadmium Grignard reagent in 60% yield.

p-Hydroxyisovalerophenone (Close *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1265) on the Clemmensen reduction afforded a 60% yield of *p*-isoamylphenol (Baranger, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1931, 49, 1213). This was hydrogenated in a Parr bomb at 1500 lbs. pressure at 150° to furnish 4-isoamylcyclohexanol in 80% yield in the presence of Raney nickel. 4-isoAmylcyclohexanol was converted into the corresponding bromide, by boiling with hydrobromic sulphuric acid mixture.

Propionitrile on treatment with the Grignard reagent, prepared from 4-isoamylcyclohexyl bromide, afforded 4-isoamylhexahydropropiofenone (II).

The compound (II) was reduced to 4-isoamylhexahydrophenylethyl carbinol in presence of Adam's catalyst at 60 lbs. pressure. This was converted into the bromide by phosphorus tribromide. The Grignard reagent of this bromide on reaction with 4-methoxyhexahydropropiofenone (I) afforded the tertiary alcohol (III), which was successfully dehydrated to (IV) by *p*-toluenesulphonic acid at 120°. The product was too small in quantity for separation into the isomeric forms. So it was directly hydrogenated with Adam's catalyst to (V), which could not be demethylated as the product was too small in quantity.

The compound was tested for its antirachitic property by Dr. V. N. Patwardhan, Director, Nutrition Research Laboratories, Coonoor, and was not found to possess any such property.

The following scheme indicates the method.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Hydroxybenzoic acid was prepared from salicylic acid by a modification of the method described in Organic Synthesis (Vol. 14, p. 48).

Dry potassium salicylate was suspended in liquid paraffin and heated in an oil-bath at 230°-240° for 3 hours. The product was poured into water and the aqueous layer separated; on acidification *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid was obtained as a slightly brown solid. This on crystallisation furnished the pure acid, m. p. 211-12°.

Ethyl *p*-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate was prepared according to Owen and Robins (*loc. cit.*).

4-Benzoyloxycyclohexane Carboxylic Acid.—Ethyl *p*-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate (17 g.), pulverised sodium (2.3 g.) and dry benzene (50 c.c.) were refluxed till the sodium had reacted; benzyl chloride (15 g.) was then added and the mixture was refluxed for 16 hours with the addition of dry pyridine. The pyridine, benzyl chloride and benzene were removed by steam-distillation, and the residue was extracted with ether. This was hydrolysed by alcoholic KOH directly. On removing alcohol and acidification, 4-benzoyloxycyclohexane carboxylic acid was obtained as a brown solid (8 g.). On crystallisation from ether, it melted at 109-110°. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 7.7; equiv., 235.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.7 per cent. Equiv., 234).

The *amide*, prepared as usual, had m.p. 172-75°. (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{14}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 6.0 per cent).

4-Benzoyloxyhexahydropropiophenone.—The above acid (5 g.) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (17 g.) for 3 hours. Excess of the latter was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.). This was added to a cadmium Grignard [prepared from ethyl bromide (20 g.), magnesium (4 g.), cadmium chloride (9 g.) and ether (20 c.c.)] in an atmosphere of nitrogen in three lots at 0° with stirring in course of 1 hour; the mixture was allowed to reach the room temperature at which it was stirred for a further period of 3 hours. It was decomposed with dilute H_2SO_4 and water, and extracted with benzene. After washing, drying and removal of the solvent it afforded a residue which could be distilled under reduced pressure (2mm.) yielding a semi-solid substance which was crystallised from methyl alcohol (2 g.), m.p. 55-58°. (Found: C, 77.9; H, 9.1. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.2; H, 9.0 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 121-22°. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{22}H_{26}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.1 per cent).

4-Methoxycyclohexane Carboxylic Acid.—Ethyl 4-methoxycyclohexane carboxylate was prepared according to Owen and Robins (*loc. cit.*). The above ester was hydrolysed to the acid, b.p. 150°-165°/25 mm. The long boiling point range showed that the ester consisted of stereoisomers. As the quantity was small the isomers could not be separated. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 8.8. $C_8H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 60.8; H, 8.8 per cent).

4-Methoxyhexahydropropiophenone (I).—The above acid (10 g.) and thionyl chloride (35 g.) were refluxed for 3 hours till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. After removing the excess of thionyl chloride, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 120°-140°/20 mm., yield 8 g.

To a cold solution of diethylcadmium in benzene [prepared from ethyl bromide (28 g.), magnesium (6 g.), cadmium chloride (14 g.), and ether (100 c.c.)], a benzene solution of the acid chloride from 4-methoxycyclohexane carboxylic acid (8 g.) was added in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was kept overnight and then stirred for 3 hours at 25°-35°. It was decomposed by ice and dilute H_2SO_4 and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract on drying and removal of the solvent was

distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 220° - $240^{\circ}/15$ mm., yield 3.5 g. d , 0.9772; n_D^{20} , 1.468; $(MR)_D$, 48.4 (calc. 48.3). (Found: C, 70.5; H, 10.8. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 70.7; H, 10.6 per cent).

Its *semicarbazone*, prepared as usual, had m.p. 174 - 75° . (Found: N, 17.9. $C_{11}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.7 per cent).

4-isoAmylcyclohexanol.—*p*-Hydroxyisovalerophenone, prepared according to Close *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), was reduced to *p*-isoamylphenol by the Clemmensen reduction according to Baranger (*loc. cit.*), b.p. $121^{\circ}/14$ mm. *p*-isoamylphenol was catalytically reduced to *p*-isoamylcyclohexanol in a Parr bomb (Ungnadd and Melaren, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 118), in the presence of Raney nickel as a catalyst at 1500 lbs. pressure at 150° , b.p. 155° - $165^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 13.1. $C_{11}H_{22}O$ requires C, 77.7; H, 12.9 per cent).

p-isoAmylcyclohexyl bromide was prepared from *p*-isoamylcyclohexanol (50 g.) and HBr- H_2SO_4 mixture (175 c.c.) according to the method given in "Organic Synthesis" (Vol. 19, p. 88) (20 g.), b.p. 162° - $167^{\circ}/20$ mm. (Found: Br, 34.4. $C_{11}H_{21}Br$ requires Br, 34.3 per cent).

4-isoAmylhexahydropropiofenone (II).—A Grignard reagent was prepared from *p*-isoamylcyclohexyl bromide (34 g.) magnesium (3.5 g.), and ether (150 c.c.). To this solution propionitrile (8 g.) was added with stirring at 0° . The mixture was kept overnight, decomposed by ice and ammonium chloride, and extracted with ether. The ether extract on drying and removal of the solvent afforded a residue which was distilled under reduced pressure, (20 g.), b.p. 130° - $135^{\circ}/5$ mm. d , 0.9979; n_D^{20} , 1.94; $(MR)_D$, 64.9 (calc. 65.1). (Found: C, 79.7; H, 12.5. $C_{14}H_{26}O$ requires C, 80.0; H, 12.4 per cent).

Its *semicarbazone*, prepared as usual, had m.p. 193 - 94° . (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{15}H_{29}ON_3$ requires N, 15.7 per cent).

4-isoAmylhexahydrophenylethyl Carbinol.—The compound (II, 19 g.) was hydrogenated over platinum oxide (4 g.) as a catalyst for 10 hours at 60 lbs. pressure. The carbinol formed had b.p. 150° - $164^{\circ}/25$ mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 13.1. $C_{14}H_{28}O$ requires C, 79.3; H, 13.7 per cent).

Ethyl-p-isoamylhexahydrobenzyl Bromide.—The preceding compound (10 g.), PBr_3 (7 g.) and benzene (25 c.c.) were mixed and kept overnight, and on the next day refluxed for 2 hours. The contents were poured into ice-water, and extracted with ether. The ether extract after drying and removing the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 120° - $150^{\circ}/35$ mm., yield 5.5 g. (Found: Br, 28.1. $C_{14}H_{27}Br$ requires Br, 28.6 per cent).

1: *2-Diethyl-1-(4-methoxycyclohexyl) - 2 - (4-isoamylcyclohexyl)-ethylene* (IV).—The compound (I, 3 g.) was added to the Grignard reagent {prepared from the above (5 g.), magnesium (0.5 g.) and ether (50 c.c.)}, cooled to 0° . It was kept overnight and refluxed for 2 hours. The product was decomposed by ice-sulphuric acid, and extracted with ether. The ether extract, after drying and removing the solvent, furnished an oily product (3.5 g.), **1**: *2-diethyl-1-(4-methoxycyclohexyl)-2-(4-isoamylcyclohexyl)-ethanol* (III).

The above product (3.5 g.) was dehydrated by heating the mixture in an oil-bath at 120°-125° with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (1 g.) for 3 hours. The contents were then poured into water, extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution, followed by water. The ether extract after drying and removing the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 185°-190°/3 mm., (2 g.), affording a mixture of red oil and a yellow solid which sublimed at the beginning of the distillation. The solid was in all probability an isomer but was small in quantity for isolation. (Found: C, 82.5; H, 12.5. $C_{24}H_{44}O$ requires C, 82.8; H, 12.6 per cent).

1:2-Diethyl-1-(4-methoxycyclohexyl)-2-(4-isoamylcyclohexyl)-ethane (V).—The above compound (IV, 2 g.) was then reduced to 1:2-diethyl-1-(4-methoxycyclohexyl)-2-(4-isoamylcyclohexyl)-ethane by platinum oxide as a catalyst (0.5 g.) at 60 lbs. pressure and had b.p. 195°/3 mm., yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 13.2. $C_{24}H_{44}O$ requires C, 82.3; H, 13.1 per cent).

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